

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HARGENRADER****FIRST NAME: WILLIAM****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 2016 on Windows 10

ACADEMIC WRITING FUNDAMENTALS

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D is an introductory course that reviews the fundamentals of academic writing, proper English, and the rules of style and ensures the student has the necessary skills to complete the course work at the Ph.D. level to include completion of the program. The main focus of the first period has been on actionable standardization, how to employ it and the reasons for doing so.

2) STANDARDIZATION

In watching the video provided, the instructor demonstrates how to use styles in Word (citation). One of the main purposes of using styles is to bring an element of standardization to the process.

Standardization is highly valuable from multiple perspectives as it is used “to bring into conformity, especially in order to assure consistency and regularity” (Merriam-Webster 2021).

From the perspective of the student, standardization allows them to organize their thoughts, share knowledge effectively, save time and resources by quickly reproducing templates, and allowing them to clearly communicate their thoughts and “and ensure consistency in your written output (EUCLID 2019, 24).

From an organizational perspective, one could make a clear case for the benefit of standardization by painting the picture of what it would look like for 100 students to turn

in work without standardization. There would most likely be 100 different variations on the underlying structure of the work were it not for the default settings on the word processing software, but nevertheless it would increase the time, attention, and effort for professors to review the work.

By employing basic standardization as demonstrated in the video, more time can be focused on the quality of the content for both the student, professor, and the organization as a whole.

3) **CONCLUSION**

The first period of this course goes into detail across many areas including standardization, templates, styles, citations, basic principles of essay writing and leads to the major purposes of academic writing: to demonstrate knowledge gained, ability to perform tasks, and to share ideas synthesized from the course material provided.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Standardization: Merriam Webster Online. Accessed March 22, 2021.
<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/standardization>

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.